

TEXTURING IN BLENDER

GUIDELINE 2025

Developed at Architecture Institute of Hochschule Mainz following the synagogue texturing workshop (March 26, 2024) for the "kARtka z synagogą" project, in collaboration with Robert Miedziocha – Polygon Studio.

Dear Student,

This guideline shows you the workflow of texturing synagogues in Blender with the help of Adobe Substance Painter and Photoshop for the use of augmented reality. It is created for beginners that have never worked in Blender before and shows standardized requirements for AR models of synagogues.

Reading the full document before beginning your work is recommended.

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CHAPTER 0

Preparation of the model in Archicad

Step 1. Export your whole model as STL or OBJ File in Archicad and import it in Blender.

Step 2. Check your model- the amount of vertices shouldn't exceed **60.000.*** But it probably does...

Turn on the **Statistics**- the data about your uploaded model will show up.

***it shouldn't but the maximum is 70.000**

Step 3. Now it's time to reduce the amount of vertices if it's needed. Go back to your Archicad file and make decisions about the elements that can be simplified, deleted or flattened.

- 1. Get rid of any round shapes**, for example instead of round columns turn their section into octagons.
- 2. Delete the base/ surroundings** of the model if it was created for 3D printing. Leave the floor of the synagogue.
- 3. Windows**- they are the heaviest part of most models. You can try to leave them as they are, flatten them in or you're gonna replace them later with flat planes of baked texture.

Remember: You can also delete faces in blender.

Step 4. Take a look at your texturing in Archicad. **Make sure that the names of materials don't contain special characters, dots, spaces, etc.**

Step 5. Next step is gonna be **the export of your model as Wavefront (OBJ) file.** This format is recommended because it opens your model in layers created based on your previous texturing in Archicad. It makes your work in Blender much faster.

So keep in mind- if you're gonna use one texture to a couple of elements they're gonna end up on the same layer.

Export separately two halves of the synagogue and Aaron Hakodesh with Bima. Place them together.

To move elements just select objects and grab colorful arrow. To see all the elements in 2D mode choose the Y, X or Z option.

m

Step 6. Put left side (together with Torah ark and Bema) and right side of your model in two collections:

CHAPTER 1

Preparation of the model before texturing

Reminder:

In this chapter you're gonna work in Layout-workspace in Edit Mode. Three circles in the right corner are responsible for the display of your model. To switch between Object Mode and Edit Mode click Tab. To choose every element click A.

To edit points, edges or vertices in your model make sure you have the right option activated.

Step 1. To delete unwanted vertices- select the whole model (Press A) and turn on the Edit Mode (Press Tab). Click M and then choose By Distance.

Step 2. To simplify some faces. Right click and choose Tris to Quads.

**Step 3. To eliminate flat shading of some elements:
recommended for windows, door frames, smaller elements**

Select them, right click and choose Clear Sharp

Then go into Object Data Properties and choose Clear Custom Split Normals Data, set auto smooth to 30 °

Step 4. To eliminate overlapping faces choose them and move them a little bit by clicking G and X.

Reminder: Probably you're not gonna notice every one of them. You can fix it later (it's gonna be more visible after texturing).

CHAPTER 2

Texturing

Step1. It's time to choose textures for your model. Download textures for example from those websites:

<https://ambientcg.com>

<https://www.cgbookcase.com>

<https://www.textures.com>

Choose textures in 4K for bigger elements like roofs or walls. Make sure they have at least Color, NormalGL and Roughness channels.

You're gonna use NormalGL Map. The second one is unnecessary. If the texture you choose only has NormalDX Map you can easily change it for GL in Photoshop:

Just invert the green channel and then save it as a new picture.

Moreover: If you found a good texture, but you don't like its color you can also edit the Color Map in Photoshop.

You can also generate your own material and maps from picture by using **Substance 3D Sampler** or **NormalMap-Online**

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F3DTive0Urg>

<https://cpetry.github.io/NormalMap-Online/>

To avoid future mistakes please **keep all your files (Blender file and all the textures in one folder and don't change its location**. If you're gonna change the location of the textures, they're gonna go missing and turn pink like here: You'll have to assign them once again.

Step 2. Adding the ColorMap/ UV Unwrapping

Choose the first group of elements for texturing and follow this short tutorial:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mURA2g1rOSc&list=PLN9pCGuxF1FI_G1ogUYCfMWrv8B231mib&index=3

Reminder: For easier UV Editing open the Toolbar in UV Editor:

Then open Shader Editor as a second window:

You're gonna see here the chosen image:

Step 3. Adding the NormalMap and RoughnessMap:

Just grab them from the folder and paste to the Shader Editor. Connect them like that:

Make sure that Roughness and NormalMap are set for Non-Color. Press Shift+A to open the menu and look for Normal Map:

Place it between NormalMap and Principled BSDF like that:

Step 4. Elements without texture: Torah ark, Bema and crosscut:

Add **Mix Shader** and **Transparent BSDF** to make Torah ark and Bema transparent.

For the crosscut just use black color.

Step 5. Ambient Occlusion

To look for components use Shift A and Search

Step 6. Windows.

To add glass effect use those:

Step 7. Substance Painter

Reminder: More about Substance Painter in Chapter 4.

To achieve the impression of dirt and irregularity of the texture you can use Substance Painter.

To display only the part you want to texture in SP mark it and click ?

export it as STL:

Then watch this tutorial:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LZWXPg3bw7E&list=PLN9pCGuxF1Fl_G1ogUYCfMWrv8B231mib&index=8

CHAPTER 3

Baking

Reminder: Baking is the last step of your work. Before final baking, read chapters 4 and 5 to enrich your work.

To bake textures you're gonna have to create 1 Map with all the textured elements.

It means creating 1 Color Map for the whole model, and following this method 1 Roughness Map and 1 Normal Map and so on:

27041Normal.png 27041Roughness.png 27042Color.png 27042Normal.png

It should look alike:

Step 2. Baking textures is explained in this tutorial:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WNAQgQGRmgQ&list=PLN9pCGuxF1Fl_G1ogUYCfMWrv8B231mib&index=5

CHAPTER 4

Substance Painter- High Poly to Low Poly

Baking detailed elements like doors or windows

Reminder: Steps shown in the last two chapters are not obligatory, but recommended. Thanks to them you can achieve a rich and detailed model that will be lighter for the online viewer.

Step 1. Select the object (High Poly Object) you want to bake and press ? to display it. Use different colors for different parts of the model that will differ in the material used:

Make sure to vary elements that will have different arrangements of wood grains.

Step 2. Now you're gonna start creating Low Poly by adding Plane in front of your detailed element:

Then make a cuboid out of it that will overlap the High Poly:

Place both models on the separate selections:

UV Unwrap Low Poly like here:

Then do this for High Poly and Low Poly so all the location and rotation are zeroed:

ctrl+A+ All Transform

Check if Normals are reversed by activating Face Orientation:

If any faces are red, tap on Space and search for Flip, all the faces should turn blue:

Reminder: If Space button doesn't activate search option follow those steps:

Then export both models as fbx files separately using those options:

Step 3. Open Low Poly model in Substance Painter:

Step 4. Then in Texture Set Settings choose Bake Mesh Maps:

Upload High Poly model here:

After baking your Low Poly model should look like that:

Substance Painter generates all the maps automatically:

Step 5: Start texturing by adding the layer of first texture:

To vary the elements of your model follow this steps:

right click and Add black mask

right click and Add color selection

choose the part of the model

change the rotation of wood grains if needed

repeat this process with other parts of the model

Step 6. To achieve a more realistic effect try out Smart Materials and Smart Masks.

Step 7. Export textures:

Step 8. Now go back to Blender. You can already delete the High Poly model. Just mark Low Poly Model and use generated maps as usual:

Reminder: Baking is gonna work better on rounded shapes, you can offset edges in Blender or before in Archicad.

CHAPTER 5

The use of Photoshop in the reduction of details

In Photoshop you can create **transparent maps** that can be used for example for such elements:

Step 1 select the element, display it like this and make a screenshot:

Step 2. Create a texture 1024x1024px, transparent and upload the screenshot there

Delete the background and use a mask to give the shape chosen texture, then duplicate:

Save it as **png** and go back to blender.

Step 3. Create a **plane** in **Blender**. Split it to separate planes so they match your texture.

Select each plane one after another, Click P+Enter to separate them:

Add a texture to planes and UV Unwrap them properly:

Don't forget to change Blend Mode to **Alpha Blend**:

Change the rotation of the plane and you're ready to replace complicated details with your simple plane:

To render your results follow those steps:

Format

Resolution X	1920 px
Y	1080 px
%	100%
Aspect X	1.000
Y	1.000

Render Region

Crop to Render Region

Frame Rate 25 fps

click ctrl b

Format

Resolution X	1920 px
Y	1080 px
%	100%
Aspect X	1.000
Y	1.000

Render Region

Crop to Render Region

Frame Rate 25 fps

Frame Range

Frame Start	1
End	250
Step	1

Time Stretching

Stereoscopy

Output

/tmp/

Saving File Extensions

Cache Result

File Format PNG

Color	BW	RGB	RGBA
Color Depth	8	16	
Compression		15%	

Image Sequence Overwrite

Placeholders

Color Management

Denoise

Render

Noise Threshold	0.0100
Max Samples	256
Min Samples	0
Time Limit	0 sec

Denoise

Path Guiding

Lights

Advanced

Light Paths

Volumes

Curves

Simplify

Motion Blur

Film

Exposure 1.00

Pixel Filter

Type	Blackman-Harris
Width	1.50 px

Transparent

Transparent Glass

Roughness Threshold 0.10

Performance

At the end choose Rendering-Render to start the rendering process

Here you're gonna find exemplary Blender File and mentioned YouTube Tutorials:

<https://seafile.rlp.net/d/8037234abe45465695e7/>

Youtube Playlist:

(please add here any other tutorials that you found helpful)

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLN9pCGuxF1FI_G1ogUYCfMWrv8B231mib&jct=xPOA3CXg7RxEbhNEwH1X_A